

Table S2 Comparison of selected features between internal and external validation.

	Internal validation (n=100)	External validation (n=77)	P value
Age (y, mean (SD))	67.5(14.65)	64.1(19.19)	0.114*
CVC (n, %)	41(41.00%)	37(47.44%)	0.447**
Duration of ICU stay (days, mean (SD))	23.0(36.53)	17.8(22.62)	0.295*
Abdominal surgery (n, %)	53(53.00%)	37(48.05%)	0.514**
Immunosuppressive drugs (n, %)	27(27.00%)	17(7.79%)	0.453**
Solid cancer (n, %)	21(21.00%)	14(18.18%)	0.641**
Chemotherapy (n, %)	20(20.00%)	9(11.69%)	0.139**
Antibiotic therapy (n, %)	84(84.00%)	64(83.12%)	0.875**
PCT (ng/ml, median (IQR))	2.43(0.64, 16.22)	1.1(0.33,13.81)	0.087***
CRP (mg/l, mean (SD))	100.5(59.37)	110.9(86.45)	0.034*
WBC count (10 ⁹ /L, median (IQR))	10.85(6.73, 16.21)	11.25(5.78, 14.62)	0.869***
Neutrophil count (10 ⁹ /L, median (IQR))	8.0(5.28, 14.16)	9.56(4.26, 13.22)	0.895***
Monocyte count (10 ⁹ /L, median (IQR))	0.55(0.23, 0.95)	0.51(0.31, 0.79)	0.866***
TPN (n, %)	38(38.00%)	29(37.18%)	0.963**
Lymphocyte count (10 ⁹ /L, mean (SD))	0.9(0.80)	1.1(1.35)	0.305*
Platelet count (10 ⁹ /L, mean (SD))	165.1(115.92)	180.0(133.82)	0.488*
Hemoglobin (g/L, mean (SD))	97.5(18.07)	101.1(18.06)	0.237*
Total bilirubin (μmol/L, median (IQR))	14.30(8.90, 34.35)	14.35(10.43, 31.95)	0.543***

Definition of abbreviations: y: years; TPN: Total parenteral nutrition; CVC: central venous catheter; WBC: white blood cell; PCT: procalcitonin; CRP: C-reactive protein; ICU: intensive care unit; IQR: interquartile range; SD: standard deviation; *The t-test for metric variable if data are normally distributed; **the Chi-square test (big sample size) and Fisher's exact test (small sample size) for categorical variables; ***the Mann-Whitney U-test for metric variables if data are not normally distributed.